

TABLE 2—4-THIAZOLIDINONES (1)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M p. °C	Antibacterial activity	
				<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	160	-	+
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	178	-	++
3.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	175	+	+
4.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	H	218	+	++
5.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	150	-	-
6.	-3NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	H	115	-	-
7.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	H	118	+	+
8.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	125	-	+
9.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	H	176	+	++
10.	3,4-CH ₂ (O).C ₆ H ₃	H	160	-	-
11.	-4OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	215	-	-
12.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃).C ₆ H ₃	H	220	+	+
13.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₂ .COOH	116	+	+
14.	-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	159	+	++
15.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	104	++	++
16.	-5.Br.2OH.C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	129	-	-
17.	-4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	173	-	+
18.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	175	-	+
19.	-4.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	105	-	+
20.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	108	+	++
21.	-4.OH.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	120	-	-
22.	3,4-CH ₂ (O).C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	177	+	+
23.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	115	-	-
24.	-3,4-di(OCH ₃).C ₆ H ₃	-CH ₂ .COOH	110	+	++

C, H, N analyses were within $\pm 0.5\%$ theoretical values. Yield 55-60%.
Other notations same as in Table 1.

reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and the product (II) crystallised from ethanol (95%). Melting point, yield and bacterial activity of II are given in Table 2.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds I and II were tested for antibacterial activities by nutrient agar plate diffusion technique, dimethyl formamide used as solvent and the compounds found to be active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the thiazolidinones were elucidated on the basis of ir spectral data. Schiff bases generally give a strong sharp band at 1630-1615 cm^{-1} (C=N stretch). This band is lost in the formation of thiazolidinones and strong bands at 1750 and 1760 cm^{-1} were characteristic for the carbonyl stretching frequency for thiazolidinone ring system.

It has been observed that in the primary screening of bactericidal activity, the *para* position of phenyl is more potent than *ortho* and *meta*. It has also been observed that introduction of bromine in the phenyl ring increases the activity of 4-thiazolidinones.

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References

- W. J. DORAN and H. A. SHONLE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 193.
- L. C. CHEMOY, R. R. SMITH and S. B. BLINKHEY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 61.
- G. L. WILLEY, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1955, 10, 466.
- R. R. ASTIK, J. N. ACHARYA and G. B. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 272.
- D. R. PATEL, P. S. SATPATHI, P. B. PATEL and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Inst. Chem., Calcutta*, 1976, 48, 305.
- P. HERY, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1952, 7, 117.
- A. R. SURRY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3354.
- H. D. TRAUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3436.
- H. K. SHUKLA, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1182.
- G. O. HENDRICKS, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 762.
- J. R. GEISY, French Pat., 1395069, 1965 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 6936).
- N. C. DESAI, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 771.
- L. CONTI, *Bull. Sci. Fac. Chim. Ind. Bologna*, 1964, 22, 13 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 61, 4253).

Polyphenolic Constituents of *Rhus mysorensis* leaves

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RHUS *mysorensis* (Heyne) (family Anacardiaceae), a thorny shrub distributed in Deccan hill country was not examined earlier for its flavonoid constituents. The present work deals with the chemical examination of *R. mysorensis* leaves. The isolation

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of these flavonoids along with their 3-*o*-rhamnosides and a biflavonoid, shows that the leaves of *R. mysorensis* is enriched with flavonoids and flavonoid glycosides in major amounts.

Experimental

1.5 kg shade dried leaves were successively extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), benzene and acetone. The vacuum dried acetone extract on alkali fractionation with (a) 2% Na₂CO₃ and (b) 2% NaOH solution, and neutralisation with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded a solid mixture containing several flavonoid components.

The three major flavonoids were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) of the ethyl acetate soluble portion of the above mixture using benzene-acetone (2 : 8, 5 : 5, 8 : 2) as eluent. The three flavonoids were purified by preparative paper chromatography using ethanol-acetic acid-water (40 : 13 : 30) as irrigating solvent.

Results and Discussion

The above flavonoids are identified as myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol by R_f value uv and ir, pmr and mass spectra of their acetates. The identity of the compounds was also confirmed by co-tlc using authentic specimens.

The higher R_f band of the solid mixture in ppc was further purified by preparative tlc (silica gel G) with benzene : pyridine : formic acid (40 : 10 : 2) and the major band was cut and eluted with pure methanol and recrystallised. It is identified as a biflavonoid containing two aepiginin units joined by a C—O—C linkage as 4'—0—6" which is identical to hinokiflavone. This is further confirmed by m.p., colour reactions and nmr data compared with an authentic specimen.

The methanol extract separated by column chromatography and the major eluent was evaporated with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate insoluble portion was separated and purified by preparative pc (40 : 13 : 30, ethanol-acetic acid-water) gave three flavonoid glycosides which were subjected to various colour reactions, uv fluorescence and hydrolysis and characterisation of hydrolytic products. All were found to be 3-*o*-glycosides and the single sugar was rhamnose. The aglycones were identified as myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol.

The identity of the three glycosides as Myricetin-3-*o*-rhamnoside, Quercetin-3-*o*-rhamnoside, and Kaempferol-3-*o*-rhamnoside was confirmed R_f, m.p. and λ_{max} by direct comparison with authentic samples. All the above compounds are isolated for the first time from this species.

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References

1. "The Flavonoids", eds. J. B. HARBOURNE, T. J. MABRY and H. MABRY, Chapman and Hall, London.
2. J. S. GAMBLE, "Flora of the Presidency of Madras", Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta, Vol. 1.
3. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids, Springer-Verlag, New York.
4. T. A. GEISSMAN, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", Pergamon Press, London.
5. J. B. HARBOURNE, "The Comparative Biochemistry of Flavonoids", Academic Press, London.

3-(1,1-Dimethylallyl) Xanthyletin from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng

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MURRAYA *koenigii* is known to be the richest source of carbazole alkaloids¹. Recent investigation reveals the presence of a coumarin from the petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the stem bark of *M. koenigii*. The coumarin has been identified as 3-(1,1-dimethylallyl) xanthyletin (I) which was previously isolated from *Boenninghausenia albiflora*².

The compound (I) (M⁺, 296), m.p. 100° was found homogeneous by tlc and mass spectrometry. It showed λ_{max} (EtOH) 226, 267, 346 nm (log ε 4.3, 4.3 and 4.1); ν_{max} (KBr) displayed peaks at 1720 (coumarin carbonyl) 1600, 1510 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (100 MHz, solvent CDCl₃, standard Me₄Si), 7.4 (1H, s, C-4), 7.0 (1H, s, C-5), 6.72 (1H, s, C-8), 1.43 (12H, s, four methyl groups), 5.6 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 3'-H) and 6.3 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 4'-H). The other signals consisted of an ABX system are (H_A, 5.03, q, J_{AX} 18 Hz; H_B, 5.08, q, J_{BX} 10Hz; H_X, 6.2, q, J_{AB} 1 Hz). The mass spectra of the compound showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 296. The base peak appeared at m/e 281 (M-15) represented by the ionic species (II). The other significant peak is at m/e 253 (M-15-28) (M⁺, Me-CO).

The production of formaldehyde in Lemieux-Rudoloff test³ supports the presence of a terminal methylene group in the side chain.

Finally the structure has been determined from ¹³C nmr (20 MHz, CDCl₃) detailed in Table 1.